

PARENTAL COPING AND SUPPORT STRATEGIES IN RAISING CHILDREN WITH DYSLEXIA

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the strategies employed by parents in supporting children diagnosed with dyslexia, a specific learning disability that affects reading, spelling, and language processing. Despite growing awareness of dyslexia in Malaysia, limited research has examined parental roles in addressing its educational and emotional challenges. Using a qualitative case study design, five parents from a selected non-governmental organization (NGO) located in Kuala Lumpur were purposively selected. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews and analyzed thematically using Braun and Clarke's (2006) framework. Two overarching themes emerged: (1) Family Dynamics and Support and (2) Coping and Adaptation. The first theme highlights the importance of spousal collaboration and extended family involvement in managing daily caregiving demands. The second theme reveals parents' adaptive responses, including faith-based acceptance, home-based learning approaches, and emphasis on developing life skills beyond academics. Findings indicate that parents serve as both advocates and educators, often compensating for gaps in institutional support. Their reliance on religious faith, emotional resilience, and creative educational strategies reflects a culturally embedded model of coping and empowerment. The study underscores the need for systematic support programs, teacher training, and inclusive educational policies to strengthen school-family collaboration. These insights contribute to understanding the lived experiences of Malaysian parents raising children with dyslexia and highlight implications for developing family-centred intervention frameworks and policies that foster academic and emotional well-being among dyslexic learners.

Keywords: coping, dyslexia, learning disability, parental support, qualitative study

INTRODUCTION

Learning disabilities (LDs) are neurodevelopmental disorders with a profound global impact. Recent statistics indicate that dyslexia affects approximately 10% of the population worldwide, translating to roughly 780 million individuals (Abu Omar et al., 2024; Ambitions, 2025; Zauderer, 2026). Characterized by persistent difficulties in acquiring basic academic skills, such as reading, spelling, and decoding, dyslexia occurs despite normal or above-average intelligence (Thakran, 2015; Vidyadharan & Tharayil, 2019; Ridzal et al., 2023). As a lifelong condition, it influences not only educational performance but also social development and daily functioning (Ali & Rafi, 2016). Furthermore, it often coexists with other developmental or

behavioral conditions, compounding the challenges faced by both affected children and their families.

Parenting a child with dyslexia can be both demanding and transformative, profoundly affecting caregivers' emotional, social, and psychological well-being (Ridzal et al., 2023). Parents frequently serve as advocates, educators, and emotional anchors, navigating a complex educational system while managing their child's behavioral and self-esteem challenges (Leslie et al., 2024). In Malaysia, however, limited understanding of dyslexia among parents and teachers often leads to misconceptions, delayed diagnoses, and insufficient support for children with learning difficulties (Alias et al., 2015). This lack of awareness contributes to societal stigma and isolation, frequently resulting in psychological distress, anxiety, and frustration among caregivers, which are exacerbated by the financial and logistical burdens of obtaining specialized assistance (Isa et al., 2017; Sulaiman & Zakaria, 2024).

PROBLEM STATEMENT AND RESEARCH GAP

Despite these significant challenges, Malaysian parents exhibit remarkable resilience, employing various coping mechanisms, such as religious faith, family support, and acceptance, to manage stress (Nesen & Bakar, 2021; Norsa'adah et al., 2025). However, while recent scholarship has begun to address the educational and psychological aspects of dyslexia, a notable research gap remains regarding the lived experiences and coping strategies of Malaysian parents. Much of the existing literature emphasizes teacher preparedness, intervention programs, or instructional design, giving limited attention to the emotional, social, and cultural contexts that shape parental adaptation (Alias et al., 2015; Sulaiman & Zakaria, 2024).

Recent advancements in localized assistive technologies highlight a shift toward accessible, home-based dyslexia management in Malaysia, though persistent systemic barriers limit their full potential. Researchers have developed various digital tools tailored to the local context to help bridge existing institutional gaps. These innovations range from early screening applications like DysScreen, which empowers caregivers to self-screen young children in dual languages (Malay and English) while overcoming the geographical and financial barriers associated with formal assessments, to learning support tools like the ReaDys speech-to-text platform and mobile-based multisensory apps (Abu Bakar et al., 2024; Ramlan et al., 2023). While these technologies effectively promote independent learning, early identification, and literacy outcomes, their real-world impact is often hindered by structural limitations. Families continue to face practical hurdles, including the high cost of comprehensive clinical diagnoses, inconsistent digital accessibility, and a persistent lack of specialized teacher training needed to integrate these tools into mainstream inclusive education.

Given these limitations, more empirical studies are needed to examine how Malaysian parents navigate dyslexia management, balancing educational, emotional, and cultural demands within their family contexts. Understanding these adaptive strategies will be crucial for developing culturally responsive intervention models and strengthening family-school partnerships in dyslexia education.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE AND QUESTION

This gap underscores the critical need for a more holistic exploration of how parents balance educational, emotional, and cultural demands while navigating the intertwined challenges of stigma and limited institutional support in Malaysia. Therefore, this study aims to explore and describe the coping mechanisms and support strategies of Malaysian parents raising children with dyslexia. To address this gap, the study is guided by the following central research question: *What strategies do parents employ to support their dyslexic children within the Malaysian socio-cultural context?*

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The findings of this study hold profound significance for parents, educators, and mental health professionals by offering deep insights into the emotional, social, and practical challenges families face. By demonstrating how parental resilience is deeply intertwined with cultural interdependence, extended kinship networks, and faith-based meaning-making, this research explicitly challenges individualistic, Western-centric frameworks of coping. In doing so, it advances existing knowledge by moving beyond primarily confirmatory research to propose a Culturally Responsive Socioecological Model of Parental Coping for Dyslexia.

Furthermore, the findings contribute directly to the development of inclusive education policy in Malaysia by providing a critical evidence base for systemic reform. By underscoring the structural barriers parents face, the research advocates for specific policy mandates that integrate specialized dyslexia training into mainstream teacher education and formalize school-family partnerships. Ultimately, this study seeks to foster empathy, transition from fragmented frameworks to unified, publicly accessible support systems, and enhance equitable support for all dyslexic learners across socioeconomic backgrounds.

LITERATURE REVIEW

CONCEPTUALIZING DYSLEXIA

Dyslexia is a specific learning disorder that affects reading, spelling, and writing skills, often despite normal intelligence and adequate educational exposure. It is neurobiological in origin and manifests through difficulties in phonological processing, decoding, and word recognition (Rabindran & Madanagopal, 2020). According to Thakran (2015), dyslexia is not a reflection of intellectual deficiency but rather a processing difference that affects how individuals perceive and interpret written language. Ali and Rafi (2016) emphasized that children with dyslexia require instructional approaches that are highly structured, multisensory, and individualized to address these unique learning barriers effectively.

The broader discourse on learning disabilities highlights the importance of early diagnosis and specialized instruction to prevent secondary emotional and behavioural issues. Vidyadharan and Tharayil (2019) argued that conventional schooling often misidentifies learning disorders as poor academic performance, underscoring the need to rethink diagnostic frameworks and intervention strategies. Within this context, dyslexia should be viewed not solely as a cognitive limitation but as a lifelong learning difference that necessitates continuous adaptation and support from both educators and caregivers.

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND EMOTIONAL IMPACTS OF DYSLEXIA

The psychosocial burden of dyslexia cascades beyond the child's academic struggles, deeply affecting the entire family unit through intertwined emotional strain and social stigma. Children with dyslexia often experience significant emotional and psychological challenges due to persistent academic failure and social stigma. Studies have shown that such difficulties can result in frustration, anxiety, and low self-esteem, ultimately affecting their overall psychological development (Ridzal et al., 2023). The social consequences extend to parents as well, who frequently report high levels of stress, guilt, and helplessness. Sulaiman and Zakaria (2024) found that Malaysian caregivers of dyslexic children commonly face stigmatization and isolation, which compound existing emotional burdens and strain family relationships.

Isa et al. (2017) and Norsa'adah et al. (2025) similarly reported that caregivers of children with learning disabilities often experience elevated stress levels due to uncertainty about their children's educational progress and limited access to professional support. These findings emphasize the need for integrated psychological interventions that address both child- and parent-related well-being.

The systemic nature of these challenges is corroborated by the WHO-UNICEF (2023) *Global Report on Children with Developmental Disabilities*, which emphasizes that children with developmental disorders globally continue to experience stigmatization, barriers to access health care, and profound inequalities in health and education outcomes. Synthesizing these high-impact international perspectives with local findings (Isa et al., 2017; Sulaiman & Zakaria, 2024) reveals that the psychosocial burden of dyslexia is not merely an individual cognitive issue, but a systemic failing that necessitates comprehensive, family-centered support structures.

PARENTAL COPING AND RESILIENCE

Parents of children with dyslexia employ diverse coping strategies to manage stress and maintain family stability. Isa et al. (2017) found that Malay caregivers frequently adopt problem-focused coping mechanisms, such as seeking professional advice or acquiring new teaching skills. Religious and spiritual coping, characterized by acceptance and positive reinterpretation of life challenges, remains a central element in the Malaysian cultural context (Nesen & Bakar, 2021). Such coping mechanisms promote endurance and foster optimism in managing the child's learning difficulties.

Hidayati et al. (2023) highlighted the evolving role of fathers in supporting children with dyslexia, suggesting that paternal involvement contributes to emotional balance and family cohesion. Similarly, Norsa'adah et al. (2025) observed that family-centered resilience, supported by social and faith-based networks, enhances the caregiving experience and mitigates emotional distress. These findings underscore the dynamic, culturally embedded nature of coping among Malaysian families.

EDUCATIONAL AND THERAPEUTIC INTERVENTIONS

Multisensory instructional methods, engaging sight, sound, touch, and movement, have demonstrated significant effectiveness in improving reading fluency and comprehension among children with dyslexia. Such approaches, when reinforced by parental involvement, enhance phonemic awareness and spelling proficiency (Ali & Rafi, 2016). Parents frequently adopt multisensory strategies at home, employing letter tiles, textured flashcards, or digital applications that integrate audio-visual cues to reinforce school learning (Yulinda et al., 2024). Psychological interventions also play a key role in addressing the emotional and behavioural dimensions of dyslexia. Parents collaborate with counsellors or psychologists to support emotional regulation, self-esteem, and coping skills, particularly in response to repeated

academic setbacks (Deshinta & Kwartarini, 2024). Behavioural strategies such as structured routines, positive reinforcement, and problem-solving activities deshelp manage frustration and task avoidance.

The integration of assistive technologies, including text-to-speech software, mobile learning applications, and phonics-based reading tools, has further revolutionized parental support practices (Lim et al., 2023). These technologies promote independent learning, vocabulary development, and engagement, especially when combined with multisensory features. Nnamani (2024) emphasized that sustainable progress requires a holistic framework integrating teacher training, school–family collaboration, and community-based support.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is theoretically grounded in Urie Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (**Bronfenbrenner, 1979**), which proposes that human development and family experiences are shaped by multiple, interacting layers of environmental systems. Rather than viewing parental challenges and coping mechanisms as isolated individual difficulties, this framework conceptualizes them as outcomes of dynamic interactions between individuals and the broader social, institutional, and cultural environments in which they are embedded.

Figure 1. Ecological Systems Framework Illustrating the Multi-Layered Factors Influencing the Lived Experiences of Parents with Dyslexia in Malaysia

By applying this perspective, the challenges faced by parents raising children with dyslexia, as well as the coping strategies they employ, are interpreted as systemic phenomena influenced by interconnected ecological contexts. As shown in Figure 1, the framework situates parents' lived experiences across four primary environmental systems:

- **The Microsystem:** The immediate environment directly impacting the parent, particularly family dynamics, spousal collaboration, and the essential involvement of extended kinship networks in sharing caregiving responsibilities (Hidayati et al., 2023; Nesen & Bakar, 2021).

- **The Mesosystem:** The interactions between the parent's microsystems, such as the critical school–family partnerships and the parental advocacy required to negotiate educational accommodations (Leslie et al., 2024).
- **The Exosystem:** The broader institutional structures that indirectly affect parents, including the accessibility of clinical diagnostic services, the availability of specialized teacher training, and fragmented inclusive education policies (Alias et al., 2015; Vasanthi, 2023).
- **The Macrosystem:** The overarching cultural and societal ideologies, which in the Malaysian context include social stigma surrounding learning disabilities, cultural norms of interdependence, and the central role of faith-based meaning-making (Isa et al., 2017; Sulaiman & Zakaria, 2024).

By viewing parental coping through this socioecological lens, resilience is understood not merely as an individual psychological trait, but as a dynamic process sustained collectively through kinship, faith, and structural adaptation.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a qualitative case study design to explore parents' support strategies provided towards raising children with dyslexia. The case study approach enables an in-depth understanding of parental experiences in supporting their children (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

Participants were recruited from a selected non-governmental organization (NGO) located in Kuala Lumpur (see Table 1). A purposive sampling technique was employed to identify information-rich participants who could provide in-depth insights into the phenomenon under study. A sample size of five parents of children with a formal diagnosis of severe dyslexia was selected. This sample size was deemed appropriate for this qualitative case study as it allowed for a deep, rich exploration of each individual's lived experience while proving sufficient to achieve data saturation, the point at which no new substantive themes or insights were emerging from the interviews. To ensure relevance and consistency, the following specific inclusion criteria were applied when purposively choosing the participants: (1) they must be Malaysian citizens; (2) they must have at least one child formally diagnosed with severe dyslexia by a qualified medical or educational professional; (3) they must be the primary caregivers directly involved in the daily care and educational support of the child; and (4) they must be willing and able to articulate their lived experiences in an interview setting.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Participants

Participant	Gender	Race	Age Range
P1	F	Malay	40-45
P2	M	Chinese	36-40
P3	F	Chinese	36-40
P4	F	Malay	40-45
P5	F	Chinese	46-50

The primary instrument used in this study was a semi-structured interview protocol designed to explore parents' support strategies in raising children with dyslexia. The protocol included open-ended and probing questions to encourage detailed, reflective responses while maintaining focus on the research objectives. A pilot interview was conducted with one parent to assess clarity, sequencing, and question relevance. Feedback from the pilot informed minor adjustments to wording and flow, enhancing the protocol's reliability, comprehensiveness, and suitability for capturing rich qualitative data during the main interviews.

Data were collected through semi-structured interviews conducted individually, either face-to-face or via Google Meet, based on participant preference. Each session lasted 45–90 minutes and was audio-recorded with consent. Participants were briefed on the study's purpose, confidentiality, and voluntary participation before signing informed consent forms. Interviews followed an established protocol and were transcribed verbatim for analysis. Thematic analysis, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase framework, was employed to identify, code, and refine emerging themes reflecting parents' experiences. Specifically, transcripts were first read multiple times for familiarization. Initial codes were generated line-by-line to capture parents' specific actions and emotional responses. These codes were then collated into potential subthemes (e.g., spousal teamwork, faith-driven acceptance). Finally, subthemes were reviewed and refined into the two overarching themes presented in this study. To ensure the trustworthiness of the findings, rigorous steps were implemented across four key criteria. *Credibility* was established through member checking, wherein participants were given the opportunity to review their transcripts to confirm the accuracy of their shared experiences. *Dependability* and *confirmability* were ensured by maintaining a detailed audit trail documenting all methodological decisions, alongside reflexive journaling to acknowledge and mitigate researcher bias. Furthermore, consistency was verified across transcripts by independently reviewing codes and discussing emerging themes until consensus was reached. Finally, *transferability* was supported by providing rich, thick descriptions of the participants' demographics, contexts, and verbatim narratives, allowing readers to evaluate the applicability of the findings to other settings.

RESULTS

Table 2 presents the themes and subthemes derived on the strategies parents employ to support their dyslexic children. Two overarching themes were identified. The first, *Family Dynamics and Support*, underscores the importance of spousal collaboration, where parents jointly manage their child's needs, and extended family involvement, where relatives provide additional emotional and practical support. The second, *Coping and Adaptation*, reflects the ways parents adjust to their child's condition, including faith-based acceptance through reliance on spiritual beliefs, home-based learning approaches tailored to the child's needs, and an emphasis on life skills that enable greater independence in daily life. Collectively, these themes demonstrate the multifaceted strategies parents adopt to nurture and support their dyslexic children.

Table 2. Themes And Subthemes on Parents' Strategies to Support Their Dyslexic Children

Research Question	Theme	Subtheme	Description
"What strategies do parents employ to support their dyslexic children?"	Theme 1: Family Dynamics and Support		The ways in which immediate and extended family members engage in sharing caregiving responsibilities to manage the child's needs.
		Subtheme 1: Spousal Collaboration	The degree of teamwork and shared responsibility between spouses in managing their child's educational and daily needs.
	Subtheme 2: Extended Family Involvement	The practical and emotional support provided by broader kinship networks, particularly grandparents, to lighten the caregiving load.	
	Theme 2: Coping and Adaptation		The emotional and practical strategies parents develop to manage stress and nurture their child's abilities.
		Subtheme 1: Faith-Based Acceptance	Reliance on spiritual beliefs and religious reframing to find meaning, strength, and emotional relief amid uncertainty.
		Subtheme 2: Home-Based Learning Approaches	The use of creative, individualized, and play-based educational methods at home to compensate for formal learning gaps.
Subtheme 3: Focus on Life Skills		Prioritizing practical independence, household responsibilities, and personal strengths over purely academic	

achievements to build the child's self-confidence.

THEME 1: FAMILY DYNAMICS AND SUPPORT

Family support emerged as a crucial factor in helping parents navigate the challenges of raising a child with dyslexia. This theme explores the different roles played by spouses and extended family members, and how their involvement impacted the parents' emotional well-being and ability to support their child. While some families demonstrated strong collaboration and mutual support, others reflected more traditional or uneven distributions of caregiving responsibilities. These dynamics significantly shaped how effectively parents could respond to their child's needs, highlighting both barriers and enablers in the family environment.

Subtheme 1: Spousal Collaboration

The extent of spousal involvement varied widely among participants. Some mothers reported carrying the majority of caregiving and educational responsibilities, often due to their husbands' limited engagement or traditional views of gender roles. One parent commented, indicating minimal emotional or practical involvement.

"He's a typical husband... [he is] more focused on being the breadwinner . "
(P1)

Another parent shared the following sentiment, reflecting a sense of isolation in decision-making:

"I think my husband always just leaves everything to me," (P3)

In contrast, other couples reported a stronger sense of teamwork and shared responsibility. For example, one participant emphasized collaborative parenting:

"My husband and I work together as a team. We face everything as a family."
(P4)

Another participant shared that they took turns, which helped ease the burden and allowed for more balanced support:

"My husband and I... we take turns," (P4)

These findings underscore the importance of shared parental responsibility, as consistent and unified support systems can significantly improve the caregiving experience and outcomes for the child.

Subtheme 2: Extended Family Involvement

Extended family members, particularly grandparents, often played an important role in providing emotional and practical support. Some participants described how their own parents stepped in to assist with caregiving, especially during busy or stressful periods. One participant shared the support her parents offered, reflecting their deep concern and awareness of the situation:

"My parents were willing to move and stay at my house to help look after my kids." (P1)

Others noted the positive influence of extended relatives, which created a nurturing environment for the child.

[With] his grandfather and siblings... many people love [and support] him." (P2)

This kind of support not only helped lighten the load on primary caregivers but also contributed to the child's sense of belonging and emotional security. These accounts provide the evidence to show that a strong family network can act as a vital buffer against the daily challenges of raising a child with dyslexia.

THEME 2: COPING AND ADAPTATION

This theme explores the various ways parents adapted to the demands of raising a child with dyslexia, highlighting emotional coping strategies and practical approaches to supporting learning and development at home. As formal support systems were often limited or delayed, many parents developed their own mechanisms to manage stress and meet their child's needs. These coping methods ranged from faith-based acceptance to creative educational practices and a shift in focus from academic achievement to life skills. These adaptive strategies illustrate how parents worked within their means and circumstances to nurture their children.

Subtheme 1: Faith-Based Acceptance

Many parents turned to faith as a source of strength and acceptance. Religious beliefs helped them find meaning in their challenges and offered emotional relief in moments of uncertainty. One parent reflected on divine will, revealing a deep sense of spiritual surrender:

"If it's destined that she has to enter the PPKI (Special Education Program), it's okay. I'll accept it, because what matters most is that she can survive." (P1)

Another participant emphasized gratitude over disappointment:

"No matter what, I'm still grateful because I have a child," (P1)

This faith-based outlook served as a critical coping mechanism, enabling parents to maintain hope and remain emotionally stable amid the difficulties.

Subtheme 2: Home-Based Learning Approaches

With limited access to formal interventions, parents often turned to home-based learning strategies tailored to their child's needs. Many used educational apps, videos, and play-based methods to make learning more engaging and less stressful for the dyslexic child. One parent's account revealed both the effort and trial-and-error process involved:

"I subscribed to the Lingokids app... but she ended up watching YouTube instead." (P1)

Others emphasized a non-coercive approach:

"If he wants to read... I never force him, because I feel that if I try too hard, he'll reject it." (P3)

Learning through play, puzzles, and interactive games was frequently used to improve dyslexic children's focus and comprehension in a stress-free environment. These creative and individualized approaches reflect parents' strong commitment to supporting their dyslexic

children's development despite institutional gaps, reinforcing the importance of flexible, child-centred learning models.

"Back then, I used to teach him Math, Malay, and English. His mother would teach Chinese... and that's how we managed. Now, when he gets home, I get him to do some gym activities." (P2)

I can only teach or get him to learn through play, like games or puzzles. That's the only way that helps him learn. We homeschool... so he can study in a quiet and calm environment, where he's able to focus better. I give him videos to watch... something educational to help with his learning. (P5)

Subtheme 3: Focus on Life Skills

Recognizing that academic success might not fully capture their child's potential, many parents chose to prioritize life skills and practical independence. This included involving their children in household tasks, establishing routines, and encouraging personal strengths such as art or observation skills. One parent reflected on this approach, expressing appreciation for their child's contributions beyond schoolwork:

"He does well with tasks like washing the dishes and sweeping the floor." (P2)

Another parent explained that this approach was an effort to foster responsibility and inclusion, helping the child feel normal and equal to other children. This shift in focus reflects an understanding that self-confidence and daily functioning are just as essential as academic achievement for the long-term development of children with dyslexia. These strategies illustrate how parents broaden their definition of success to better align with their child's unique capabilities:

"He's more into drawing... but he's also fine with helping to sweep the floor." (P2)

"She has to do chores, save money, and do everything... including prayers just like everyone else. Because we also need to teach our other children how to grow and benefit together." (P4)

DISCUSSION

This study illuminates the complex processes through which Malaysian parents support children with dyslexia, a phenomenon best understood through Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory. The findings demonstrate that parental resilience is not merely an individual psychological trait, but rather a dynamic process shaped by interactions across the microsystem (spousal and extended family support), mesosystem (parent-school advocacy), and macrosystem (cultural and faith-based values).

EMOTIONAL RESILIENCE AND FAITH-BASED COPING

Consistent with earlier Malaysian studies (Isa et al., 2017; Sulaiman & Zakaria, 2024), parents in this study reported heightened emotional strain stemming from academic pressures, societal stigma, and uncertainty regarding their child's future. However, this research extends prior findings by demonstrating that parental coping goes beyond mere stress reduction into active meaning-making. Parents frequently reframed dyslexia as a test of patience, a spiritual responsibility, or a pathway for personal growth, aligning with Norsa'adah et al. (2025), who found that acceptance-based coping significantly enhances psychological endurance among caregivers.

This faith-based acceptance emerged as a particularly salient mechanism, deeply reflecting Malaysia's socio-religious macrosystem. Unlike Western literature, which often conceptualizes coping through individualistic resilience frameworks, Malaysian parents interpreted dyslexia within a collective and spiritual worldview (Isa et al., 2017; Nesen & Bakar, 2021). This supports Creswell and Poth's (2018) assertion that lived experiences are interpreted through culturally embedded lenses, suggesting that resilience among these parents is fundamentally existential, rooted in belief systems that provide coherence and purpose amid adversity.

EDUCATIONAL ENGAGEMENT, ADVOCACY, AND SYSTEMIC GAPS

Driven by these foundational beliefs, parents actively engaged in home-based learning as a compensatory response to persistent gaps in formal educational support. Mirroring the findings of Yulinda et al. (2024), caregivers adopted multisensory strategies that align with neurodevelopmental understandings of dyslexia to reinforce phonological processing and engagement. Furthermore, the integration of localized assistive technologies, such as the ReaDys platform, helped mediate frustration and support individualized learning (Lim et al., 2023; Mohamad et al., 2024).

However, unlike contexts with established dyslexia infrastructure, parents frequently expressed uncertainty regarding their own instructional competence. Limited societal understanding of dyslexia's neurobiological basis often constrains effective formal intervention, forcing parents to assume quasi-teacher roles without adequate preparation (Alias et al., 2015; Rabindran & Madanagopal, 2020). Consequently, parental advocacy emerged as both a protective strategy and a profound source of strain. Echoing Leslie et al. (2024), parents functioned as vital allies who challenged stigmatizing narratives and negotiated educational accommodations. Yet, they had to navigate fragmented exosystems characterized by limited screening and inconsistent teacher readiness (Alias et al., 2015; Vasanthi, 2023). This aligns with Nnamani's (2024) ecosystemic perspective, emphasizing that learning difficulties cannot be disentangled from institutional structures, and highlighting how the necessity for private interventions reinforces socioeconomic disparities.

CULTURAL SUPPORT SYSTEMS AND COLLECTIVE RESILIENCE

To buffer against these systemic institutional deficits and the resulting caregiving fatigue, family cohesion and extended kinship networks played a critical microsystemic role (Nesen & Bakar, 2021). The collective involvement observed here reflects Asian cultural norms of interdependence, contrasting sharply with the nuclear-family-centered caregiving models dominant in Western literature. Extended family support not only reduced parental exhaustion but also enhanced the children's emotional security, reinforcing the observation that informal networks frequently must compensate for formal institutional gaps (Alias et al., 2015).

By highlighting these specific cultural and faith-based dimensions, this study explicitly challenges predominantly individualistic, Western-centric models of parental coping. The findings demonstrate that in the Malaysian context, resilience is heavily dependent on collective interdependence and shared spiritual values. Ultimately, this expands upon current

ecosystemic models by redefining parental resilience not just as a psychological trait, but as a necessary substitute for structural support. While parental adaptability is commendable, this study cautions against romanticizing resilience in the absence of robust systemic backing. Sustainable dyslexia support requires an alignment between families, schools, and policy structures, transitioning toward equitable, inclusive models where parents are recognized as central, empowered partners rather than being forced to act as peripheral advocates compensating for systemic shortcomings.

CONCLUSION

This study explored the coping mechanisms and support strategies of Malaysian parents raising children with dyslexia. The findings reveal that parents navigate complex educational and social challenges by relying heavily on emotional resilience, faith-based meaning-making, and robust community networks. Despite confronting persistent institutional barriers and fragmented support systems, parents exhibit profound commitment and adaptability to facilitate their children's development. Ultimately, this research underscores the vital need for systemic recognition of parental roles, emphasizing that strengthening formalized partnerships among parents, educators, and policymakers is essential for fostering an inclusive, equitable, and responsive educational landscape.

While this study provides valuable insights, it is subject to certain limitations. The research focused solely on the perspectives of parents raising children with severe dyslexia, thereby excluding the viewpoints of teachers, therapists, and educational administrators. Furthermore, the sample was drawn from a specific non-governmental organization in Kuala Lumpur, which may not fully represent the experiences of parents across different Malaysian states, cultural backgrounds, or socioeconomic statuses.

To address these limitations, future studies should incorporate a larger and more diverse participant pool, including parents of children with varying degrees of dyslexia. Comparative studies integrating the perspectives of educational and medical professionals would provide a more holistic understanding of the support ecosystem. Additionally, longitudinal or mixed-method designs are recommended to examine how parental coping strategies evolve over time and interact with long-term educational interventions. Finally, policy-oriented research should critically evaluate the effectiveness of current inclusive education programs to identify and bridge service delivery gaps for families managing dyslexia in Malaysia.

THEORETICAL IMPLICATIONS

The findings of this study offer significant contextual enrichment to existing coping and resilience frameworks. By demonstrating that parental resilience in the Malaysian context is not an isolated psychological trait but is deeply embedded in cultural interdependence and socioecological factors, this research challenges purely individualistic, Western-centric models. Consequently, we propose a Culturally Responsive Socioecological Model of Parental Coping for Dyslexia. This conceptual model moves beyond traditional frameworks by organizing parental adaptation into three interconnected domains:

- **The Macrosystemic Foundation (Cultural and Spiritual Beliefs):** At the core of the model is faith-based acceptance. Spiritual reframing and religious beliefs provide the existential and emotional foundation that enables parents to manage uncertainty and sustain hope.
- **The Microsystemic Support Network (Kinship and Interdependence):** Rather than isolated caregiving, coping is sustained collectively. Spousal collaboration and the active involvement of extended family members act as vital buffers against emotional fatigue and societal stigma.

- **The Action-Oriented Adaptation (Compensatory Strategies):** Driven by their foundational beliefs and supported by their kinship networks, parents enact practical coping mechanisms, such as home-based learning approaches and a focus on life skills.

Crucially, the model posits that these proactive strategies often emerge as necessary compensatory responses to persistent systemic and institutional barriers. Ultimately, this model redefines parental resilience as a dynamic interplay between collective kinship support, faith-based meaning-making, and structural educational gaps.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

To translate these findings into actionable interventions, targeted strategies must be implemented across three key domains:

- **For Educators and Schools:** Educational institutions must transition toward active, family-centered intervention programs. Schools should establish formalized school-family partnerships by hosting regular collaborative workshops where teachers and parents co-develop individualized education plans. Furthermore, mainstream teacher education must mandate practical training on multisensory instructional methods. Schools should also be equipped to utilize and guide parents in using localized digital assistive technologies, such as the DysScreen mobile application for early, dual-language screening (Abu Bakar et al., 2024) and speech-to-text platforms like ReaDys for ongoing learning support (Ramlan et al., 2023), ensuring these tools are effectively integrated into both classroom and home-based learning environments.
- **For Policymakers:** As emphasized in the discussion, policymakers must move beyond basic awareness campaigns and enact specific mandates to unify currently fragmented support structures. Inclusive education policies must be designed to ensure equitable access to early screening, diagnosis, and comprehensive support services across all socioeconomic backgrounds. By institutionalizing this collaboration, parents can be recognized and supported as central, empowered partners in their child's educational trajectory, rather than being forced to act as peripheral advocates compensating for systemic educational shortcomings.
- **For Mental Health Professionals:** Counsellors and clinical practitioners must explicitly incorporate parental psychosocial well-being into their intervention frameworks, recognizing that the emotional burden of dyslexia deeply affects caregivers. Instead of generic stress-management advice, practitioners should design and facilitate targeted, localized caregiver support groups to reduce isolation and social stigma. Furthermore, clinical interventions should integrate acceptance-based therapy and cognitive reframing that specifically align with the Malaysian socio-religious context, leveraging parents' cultural interdependence and faith-based values as foundational tools for building family resilience.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this article.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

Nurulaamal Muhamad conducted the data collection and analysis, while Aishah Hanim Abd Karim drafted, revised, and edited the manuscript in accordance with the journal's guidelines.

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